

Original Research Article

Prevalence of Urinary Tract Infections among Asymptomatic Female Students of Nasarawa State Polytechnic Lafia, North Central Nigeria

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Abstract

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This study was designed to assess the prevalence of urinary tract infections among asymptomatic female students of Nasarawa State Polytechnic, Lafia, Nigeria. A structured questionnaire was used for demographic data collection following informed consent. A total of 214 urine and an equal number of HVS samples were collected and investigated using microscopy examination after which biochemical test was conducted on the isolates. Out of 214 samples collected. 174(81.31%) had at least one infection and the organisms isolated include *Staphylococcus aureus* which had the highest prevalence of 47(43.93%) in urine and 54(50.47%) in HVS samples, *Escherichia coli* was next with 30(28.04%) in urine and 13(12.15%) in HVS, *klebsiella* and *Proteus sp.* was 18(16.82%) and 17(15.89%) found in urine respectively, others were *Streptococcus sp.* and *Candida sp.* having equal number for both samples 9(8.41%) in urine and 20(18.69%) in HVS. *Trichomonas vaginalis* 6(5.61%) was identified only in urine samples. The age group 20-29years had the highest prevalence. Mixed and single infections were also observed. The implications of this study were discussed and highlights were made on the need for provision of hostel accommodation with good and adequate toilet facilities, creating awareness and educating students especially females on the causes, transmission pattern, aetiology of these diseases and manifestation of the infections.

Keywords: Asymptomatic Female Students, Urine, High Vaginal Swab(HVS), Urinary Tract Infection

INTRODUCTION

Urinary Tract Infection (UTI) is a common public health problem which affects both males and females. It is quite high among females due to their anatomical make up. The male urethra is about 20cm (8 inches) while the female urethra is about 4cm (1.5 inches). This will allow access to microorganism more easily than in male (Olusanyo *et al.*, 1993; Ojo and Anibijuwon, 2010) and every woman experience at least one form of urinary tract infection in their lifetime approximately 50% (Fihn, 2003). Urinary tract infections are caused by bacteria and other

microbes that enter the urethra and then the bladder. This can lead to infection, most commonly in the bladder which may spread to the kidney. Catheters, diabetes, sickle cell disease, enlarge prostate, narrowed urethra, kidney stone, immune suppress individuals and pregnancy are risk factors of urinary tract infections (Fowler, 1996; Lin and Fajard, 2008; Foster, 2008; Nicolle, 2008). Areas infected are the upper and lower urinary tract like the bladder (Cystitis) and Kidney (Pyelonephritis) (Nester *et al.*, 2004). The infection may

be asymptomatic, acute and chronic or complicated (Steiner *et al.*, 1997; WHO, 2005). *Escherichia coli* is the leading cause of acute and uncomplicated infection of the lower tract (Cystitis) in young women while *Staphylococcus spp* is known to be the main cause of bladder infection (Muder *et al.*, 2006; Kolawole *et al.*, 2006). Clinical presentation of these infections is age, sex and location of infection in the urinary tract dependent. When this bacteria eventually enters into the system, the individual starts showing some signs and symptoms which includes: painful sensations while urinating and frequent urination in case of cystitis as a result of bladder infection whereas conditions like high fever and flank pain are commonly experienced in case of kidney infection (Olaitan, 2007; Olusanyo *et al.*, 1993) others includes; lower abdominal pain, jaundice due to loss of blood, itching, formation of blisters and ulcer in the genital area, supra-pubic pain, vaginal and urethral discharge (e-medicine, 2005; Amali *et al.*, 2008). In United States urinary tract infection accounts for more than 7 million visits to clinics and hospitals each year. Previous studies reported that UTIs is one of the most common forms of hospital acquired infection (nosocomial) and the second most common infectious disease in women after gastrointestinal disorders (GID) (WHO, 2001). The infection encompasses a diverse group of clinical syndromes and diseases that differ in epidemiology, etiology, location and severity of the condition (Nester *et al.*, 2004). Infection affect various organs of the body which are involved in the production, storage and excretion of urine. It contains a variety of fluids, salts and water products among others (Ani, and Mgbechi, 2008). Thus urine and HVS culture are considered the main standard for its investigation.

Awareness on the health implication of urinary tract infection is low in Lafia, Nasarawa State and this infection has not been given due attention, therefore the aim of this study is to investigate the level of infection and awareness among female students in Nasarawa State Polytechnic.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Area

This study was conducted in Nasarawa State Polytechnic Lafia and its environ. Lafia is the capital city of Nasarawa State with three major ethnic groups and diversified languages. Lafia is a town in North-central Nigeria and has a population of 330,712 (NPC, 2006). Economic activities of the people is petty trading and agriculture. The major crops cultivated includes but not limited to yam, cassava, beniseed, and melon. Lafia is situated at 8.48° North latitude, 8.52° East longitude and 290 meters above sea level and has an average temperature of 31°C.

Ethical Considerations

Informed consent was obtained from study participants. Where applicable, landlords/caretakers were informed and permission granted for the authors to access their compounds.

Sample Collection and Analysis

A structured questionnaire was administered to each sampled student to obtain information before samples were collected, each student was enlightened on the purpose and importance of the study to them and their immediate community. Following consent from the students, a total of 214 urine and HVS samples were collected for the research. Sterile universal containers were used to collect midstream urine, while sterile swab sticks were used to collect high vaginal swab (HVS) of each volunteered student by the laboratory scientist using standard procedure (Cheesbrough, 2004).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The following results were obtained from the study.

Discussion

Microscopic examination of urine and HVS samples revealed the presence of pus cells, yeast cells, casts, calcium oxalate and epithelial cells as shown in (table 1). Out of 214 urine and HVS samples collected, 97(90.65%) and 77(71.69%) were infected respectively. In table 2 we had 174 (81.31%) that were examined to be co-infected from both urine and HVS samples. Table 3 shows the prevalence of organism isolated from both samples. *Staphylococcus aureus* was the most prevalent organism with 47(43.93%) in urine and 54(50.74%) in HVS, and this agrees with the research conducted by Andabati and Byamugisha, 2010; Ekwealor *et al.*, 2016, that *S. aureus* is high in UTI and since the patients having significant bacteriuria were asymptomatic so the situation is of utmost concern in the study area. The second most common bacteria was *Escherichia coli*, 30(28.04%) in urine and 13(12.15%) in HVS, this could be due to the close proximity of the anus to the vagina and its inherent virulence for urinary tract colonization such as its abilities to adhere to the urinary tract and its association with other microbes moving from the perineum areas contaminated with faecal microbes to the moist warmth environment of the female genitalia (Andabati and Byamugisha, 2010; Ekwealor *et al.*, 2016). The third commonest bacteria isolated was *Klebsiella sp.* 18(16.82%) and *Proteus sp.* 17(15.89%) which were found in urine samples only and this agrees with the

Table 1. Showing microscopic examination of Urine and HVS samples

Sediments	No. of occurrence in Urine sample (%)	No. of occurrence in HVS sample (%)
Pus cell	50 (46.73)	38 (35.51)
Yeast cells	14 (13.08)	20 (18.69)
Casts	12 (11.21)	02 (1.00)
Calcium oxalate	10 (9.35)	02 (1.87)
Epithelial cells	21 (19.63)	45 (42.06)

Table 2. Showing total number of co-infection from both HVS and urine samples.

Samples	No. Examined	No. infected	% Infected
Urine	107	97	90.65
HVS	107	77	71.96
Total	214	174	81.31

Table 3. Showing prevalence of organisms isolated from Urine and HVS samples.

Organisms isolated	No. of students examined	No. of organisms in urine sample (%)	No. of organisms in HVS sample (%)
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	107	47 (43.93)	54 (50.74)
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	107	30 (28.04)	13(12.15)
<i>Klebsiella sp.</i>	107	18 (16.82)	-
<i>Proteus sp.</i>	107	17 (15.89)	-
<i>Streptococcus sp.</i>	107	9 (8.41)	20 (18.69)
<i>Candida sp.</i>	107	9 (8.41)	20 (18.69)
<i>Trichomonas vaginalis</i>	107	6 (5.61)	-

Table 4. Showing mixed infections in urine and HVS samples.

Sample	No. examine	No. with single infection (%)	No. with mixed infection (%)	No. with no infection (%)
Urine	107	53 (49.53)	44 (41.12)	10 (09.35)
HVS	107	61 (51.01)	16 (14.95)	30 (28.04)
Total	214	114 (106.54)	60 (56.07)	40 (37.38)

Table 5. Showing age distribution of patients.

Age group (years)	No. examined	No. of positive samples (%)	No. of negative samples (%)
15-19	18	14 (77.78)	4 (22.22)
20-29	174	158 (90.80)	16 (09.19)
30 and above	22	11 (50.00)	11 (50.00)
Total	214	183 (85.51)	31 (14.49)

study by Baguma *et al.*, 2017 that about 40% of UTI are caused by Gram negative species, *Streptococcus sp.* and *Candida sp.* were found to be 9(8.41%) in urine and 20(18.69%) in HVS respectively while *T. vaginalis*, 6(5.61%) was found only in urine samples, and this infection is usually caused when the normal acidity of the vagina is disturbed or when sexually transmitted and this

finding concords with Lindsay *et al.*, 2005 and Fihn, 2003 who estimated that 50% of women have had one form of UTI at some point in their lives. Mixed infections was observed as presented in table 4. Based on age distribution, the result shows that age group 20-29 years had the highest prevalence of urinary tract infection 158(90.80%) and this is because the age group are

sexually active while age group 30 years and above had the lowest prevalence of 11(50.00%) as shown in table 5 and this agrees with the suggestion of O'Donell, 1994. Based on the survey, it was obvious that UTI is of public health concern in the study area and the disease had adversely affected the socio-economic life of the population. Amali *et al.* (2008) suggest that infection could have possibly occurred despite precautions taken to prevent it but the high prevalence of pathogenic organisms observed in this study may have been resulted from the unclean state of their sanitary environment and improper use of the toilets/bathrooms and its environment which could result in infection because female urine is ejected and creates great splashes which could re-introduce pathogenic organisms from the environment into their urinary opening.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this study shows that urinary tract infection is of public health concern among students of Nasarawa State Polytechnic, Nigeria. The overall prevalence of 174(81.31%) may have been as a result of the unhygienic state of the environment the students live in, as there is no provision for hostel accommodation by the school, careless and dirty habits among students, the use of communal toilet/bathrooms systems should be viewed as public risk.

RECOMMENDATIONS

From the findings of this study, it is evident that the prevalence of urinary tract infection is high and the following recommendations should be adhered to:

- ❖ Avoid sex with multiple partners and be faithful to one uninfected partner.
- ❖ Promote proper and correct use of condom and use it always with strangers.
- ❖ Treatment should involve both infected partners.
- ❖ Avoid drug abuse in order not to promote drug resistant which may have resulted to the re-infection witnessed in this study.
- ❖ Hostel accommodation should be provided and adequate toilet system instituted to avoid this communal latrine system also ensure to wipe from front to back when you go to toilet.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors are grateful to the students who gave consent of participation in this study. Landlords, caretakers and neighbors are appreciated for their tolerance and acceptance to assess the environment.

Competing Interest

Authors have declared that no competing interest exist.

Authors' contribution

All the authors contributed in this study. Angbalaga, A. G conceptualized the research, designed the study, conducted the laboratory analysis, did corrections on the draft copies and coordinated the research. Akeh A. Martins contributed in the laboratory analysis, proof read and approved the submission. Abbas A.A reviewed the manuscript and proof read the final draft. Sikiti, B. L contributed in the writing of the manuscript. All authors read the final draft and approved it for publication.

Ethical consideration

Informed consent was obtained from all study participants prior to enrollment in the study.

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